

The Radar System and Information Flow

John A. Malas¹, John A. Cortese²

*Sensors Directorate, Air Force Research Lab
2241 Avionics Circle, WPAFB, Ohio, 45433, USA*

¹john.malas@wpafb.af.mil
*MIT Lincoln Laboratory
244 Wood Street, Lexington, MA, 02420-9108, USA*
²jcort@ll.mit.edu

Abstract—The information flow through a radar system channel is studied for various component design choices including the radar measurement function, signature feature selection, and classifier decision rule. A simplified target scattering model is used to analyze the application of the information theoretical channel model.

I. INTRODUCTION

Analysis and synthesis together are necessary scientific methods within the study of systems. Riemann's classical definition of the concepts of analysis and synthesis [1] emphasizes the need to see the system as both a functioning unit and as a set of interacting parts. The ability to perform radar system component trade studies in an efficient and meaningful way demands that we study the function of any one component in the context of the system as a whole. The integration science that works at the seams between components is critical to the research of emerging signature exploitation technology. System components include hardware designs within the antenna, receiver, analog-to-digital converter, and signal processor areas as well as software designs to measurement functions, transmit waveforms, digital sampling approaches, and signal processing techniques. These radar systems also include a new list of significant design components that are related to the task of target signature measurement, feature processing, and decision algorithm performance. The use of existing systems theory prototypes such as the radar range equation are useful in studying target visibility, yet fall short in their ability to fully characterize the flow of information through the radar system as it relates to a desired specific exploitation capability. The resulting expanded trade space requires new systems theory models that analyze the component level information extraction/loss of measured signals.

Woodward and Davies [2] and Woodward [3] were the first to apply the information theoretic approach to the analysis of radar, soon after the appearance of Shannon's original work [4] on information theory. More recently Bell [5] has suggested the use of an information theoretic approach to the design of radar waveforms. Dr. Bell formulated and obtained a solution to the problem of designing a waveform that maximized the mutual information (MI) between the target impulse response (viewed as a random process) and the received signal. Recently, Leshem et al. [6] extended Bell's work to the case of multiple extended targets. Sowelam and Tewfik [7] also used

waveform design in conjunction with the Kullback-Liebler [8] criterion to distinguish between different target classes. Briles [9] applied rate distortion theory to analyze the impulse radar for use in target identification design and performance prediction. Home and Malvern [10] introduce a high level theoretical framework to calculate the information conveyed by the image of a target based on pixel values relative to the modeled fluctuations of these values. Principe, Xu, Zhao, and Fisher [11] present a framework for learning based on information theoretic criteria. Methods such as the maximum likelihood test have been used to evaluate radar signature processes for target classification performance as in the work by O'Sullivan et al [12]. This framework proposes several approximations to the Kulback-Leibler divergence that can be used to estimate statistical distances compatible with pattern matching algorithms. Malas and Pasala [13] introduce the use of MI as a similarity measure for use in radar signature database validation. Recently, there has been much interest in radars with a new architecture referred to as the MIMO (Multiple Input Multiple Output) radar [14] – [17]. It is the information theoretic approach that unifies the analysis of these radar systems.

In varying degrees the existing referenced work has presented the radar system in terms of a Markov Chain within a channel configuration and characterized the information flow within from source and sink. Tishby [18] has developed the information bottleneck approach, wherein rate-distortion theory, the Data Processing Theorem, and compression play major roles. The max-flow min-cut application to the channel problem has been studied to understand the relationship of capacity to information flow. A significant contribution of the work provided herein is the development and demonstration of a systems theory model for the study of individual information contributions of components within the radar system. This theory model is applied in an effort to generate an understanding of the relative ranking of these sources of information loss as they relate to component design.

II. APPROACH

An information theoretic theory model is presented to quantify and study the flow of information through the radar system. Fundamental systems trades associated with sensor design (bandwidth, dynamic range, and signal-to-noise ratio), classifier algorithm training, and algorithm feature design are performed to illustrate the information loss associated with these various components of the radar exploitation system.

A. Radar Information Channel Model

The radar system can be viewed within a systems model depicting the information flow through the signature sensing and processing components of a radar system as shown in Fig. 1 [19].

Fig. 1. Information Theoretic Radar Channel Model.

The relationship between the true state (H) of a target under measurement and the decision state (Q) of a classifier algorithm is the basis chosen for performance characterization. Successful flow of information results in agreement between H and Q . This channel model differs from the communications channel model in several important respects. In the communications channel the transmission signal is designed to maximize information flow through a fixed channel. In the case of the radar information channel, the problem involves the design of the channel for maximum information flow given a fixed input (the scattered field of the targets).

B. Radar Sensor Model

The use of high range resolution (HRR) radar measurements has been useful in the support of research of signature exploitation capability within airborne platforms. In view of the uncertainties in the aspect angle of the target, the HRR signature may be considered to be a random vector. Given the changing geometry relative to the target within a typical radar measurement interval, the statistics associated with the HRR random vector are often time varying. Therefore, the measured HRR signature of the target at a given time “ t ” is a realization of a multidimensional random process (time varying random vector). If the target statistics are assumed to be stationary (constant with time), the sample signatures associated with this random vector correspond to a range of aspect angles in a small window about this reference.

C. Target Scattering Model

In the high frequency regime used to obtain HRR signatures, the target may be approximated as a collection of scattering centers valid over a limited aspect window and

frequency band. These scattering centers may be considered to be localized to a point and may represent a variety of scattering phenomena ranging from specular reflection to diffraction phenomena such as edge and tip diffraction. The fields radiated by these point scatterers depend upon both temporal and spatial frequencies (angular dependence). Since the radar illuminating the target has finite bandwidth and is a one dimensional imaging system, the target is seen as a collection of contiguous swaths of range, with each range swath corresponding to a particular range. The extent of each range swath, range resolution, depends upon the signal bandwidth. For a typical extended target of interest, each range swath contains a number of scattering centers which can be widely spaced in cross-range.

The electromagnetic field obtained as a result of the interference of the scattered fields from the scattering centers appears as the signal corresponding to a particular range bin of the HRR signature. The HRR signature may be considered to be a one dimensional image of the reflectivity (or scattering) profile of the target for a given look angle and bandwidth. The mathematical definition of the HRR signature is developed from the normalized scattered field in (1) for a single frequency. In equation (1) σ is the normalized radar scattered field and R is the range to the scattering center. \vec{E}^s and \vec{E}^i are the scattered field and the incident field respectively.

$$\sigma = \lim_{R \rightarrow \infty} 4\pi R^2 \frac{\vec{E}^s}{|\vec{E}^i|} \quad (1)$$

Using scattering center modeling and the far field approximation, equation (1) can be written in terms of the target aspect angle and the transmitted wavelength as shown in equation (2) [20].

$$S(\theta, \phi, \lambda) = \sum_{m=1}^M \sqrt{\sigma_m} e^{j \frac{4\pi}{\lambda} R_m} \quad (2)$$

In equation (2) S is the band-limited frequency response of the target. Applying matched filter processing and the discrete Fourier transform, the measured HRR signature can be modelled for a given aspect angle and range of frequencies present in the transmitted waveform. The variation in signature phenomenology due to the uncertainties in the aspect angle are captured in the signal model illustrating that the HRR signature must be viewed as a random process represented here as \vec{X} . A small window of aspect angles, typically less than $5^\circ \times 5^\circ$ in azimuth and elevation around a specified aspect, is chosen for targets of interest at X-band frequencies (8-12 GHz) in the following development. The targets are electrically large with dimensions in range and cross-range of many wavelengths. In all cases the thermal noise is assumed to be additive.

D. Decision Algorithm

The algorithm used to perform the feature extraction function f in Fig. 1 is based on the principle components [21] (or modes) of the complex HRR signature process \bar{X} . The discriminant D in Fig. 1 then becomes the power associated with the projection of the sampled test signature vector from \bar{X} with the principle eigenvector (or eigenvectors) associated with our best characterization of \bar{X} . The eigenvectors of \bar{X} are estimated from the training process \bar{X}' as shown in Fig. 1.

E. Decision Rule Training

The training process component \bar{X}' in Fig. 1 represents the best possible statistical characterization of the observed signature process \bar{X} . Signature training processes must represent the radar measured signature process across a wide range of target articulations and configurations as well as under many operating conditions including clutter, obscuration, and other sources of RF interference. Construction of a signature training database derived entirely from measurements is expensive and can be an impractical proposition. It is possible to construct a signature database using electromagnetic scattering codes. However, given the complexity of typical targets and the challenge of modeling a variety of electromagnetic scattering phenomena ranging from specular reflection to edge diffraction, smooth surface diffraction etc., computation of signatures with sufficient accuracy is a challenging task [13]. Furthermore, it needs to be established that the computed signatures \bar{X}' are consistent with measured signatures \bar{X} . Within this analysis the dissimilarity of \bar{X} with \bar{X}' will be generated using scattering center decimation. The number of scattering centers associated with peak features in \bar{X} is reduced incrementally. $\bar{X}' \equiv \bar{X}$ when \bar{X} is used for the training of the decision rule d in Fig. 1.

F. Numerical Experiments

The information flow between components within the radar system is studied through several numerical experiments. The design of the sensor, decision rule training approach, and algorithm feature are varied. The information loss at each component is computed for each design configuration. The various design configurations are outlined in Table I. The baseline design configuration is as defined in Case 1 with the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) set to 20 dB. Cases 1-4 are designed to study the sensitivity of information loss within various components of the system to changes in key design parameters. In Case 1 the sensitivity to additive thermal noise is studied at baseline conditions. In Case 2 the sensitivity of component information loss is studied as a function of increasing bandwidth. In Case 3 the number of modes used to construct the signature feature (number of eigenvectors) is varied to study the effect of information loss within components. In Case 4 baseline conditions are used to study

the information loss associated with the degree of similarity between the training process \bar{X}' and the measured process \bar{X} .

TABLE I
EXPERIMENTS

Case	Appearance (in Time New Roman or Times)		
	Sensor, \bar{x}	Algorithm Feature, f	Training Process, \bar{x}'
1	Bandwidth: 500 MHz Dynamic Range: 10 Bit SNR: 0-20 dB	Mode: 1	$\bar{X}' \equiv \bar{X}$
2	Bandwidth: 100-1000 MHz Dynamic Range: 10 Bit SNR: 20 dB	Mode: 1	$\bar{X}' \equiv \bar{X}$
3	Bandwidth: 500 MHz Dynamic Range: 10 Bit SNR: 20 dB	Modes: 1-15 Cumulative	$\bar{X}' \equiv \bar{X}$
4	Bandwidth: 500 MHz Dynamic Range: 10 Bit SNR: 0-20 dB	Mode: 1	$\bar{X}' \neq \bar{X}$

III. THEORY

It is desired to quantify the impact of information loss associated with selected system components on system performance. Two theorems from information theory play key roles in our development of this relationship. The first theorem is Fano's Inequality which relates information theoretic quantities to the Probability of Error (P_e) criterion for a target classification system [22]. The second theorem is the Data Processing Inequality [22]. The Data Processing Inequality allows the analysis of the flow of information from the measured target returns through the signal processing architecture and into the decision rule algorithm, detailing where information is lost. In this manner, stages in the information processing pipeline where information is lost can be identified, analyzed and optimized, leading to improvement in overall system performance.

The discrete random variable H represents which of N possible hypotheses has occurred. For example, when $N=2$ we can have outcomes A or B. Conditioned on the generating hypothesis H , there is a typically a multidimensional encoded source \bar{X}_E which when subjected to the uncertainties associated with measurement is realized as the random radar returns from the scattering of the object under measurement. After mixing, filtering, and signal processing, these returns become the measured random signature vector \bar{X} . Typically the multidimensional random feature \bar{Y} is extracted from \bar{X} in order to support the desired function of the exploitation system. The decision rule training process \bar{X}' is used to develop a full characterization of \bar{Y} . This characterization is applied to sample measured signatures of \bar{X} to generate the random discriminant D . \bar{X}' is also used in conjunction with sparse samples from \bar{X} and to determine the optimal

algorithm decision rule d . The exploitation algorithm applies the decision rule d to D . The discrete random variable Q denotes the classifier algorithm decision of which hypothesis occurred based on the signal processed feature \vec{Y} and resulting discriminant D .

Fano's equality for the model in Fig. 1 is given in (3).

$$S(P_e) = \delta - P_e \cdot \log_2(N-1) + S(H/Q) \quad (3)$$

In (3) P_e is the probability of error of the decision rule algorithm, $S(H)$ is the Shannon entropy of the discrete random variable H . $S(H/Q)$ is the conditional entropy of H given Q . δ is a bias offset derived from symmetries in the data and decision algorithm [19], as well as the signal processing algorithm. Typically δ is small and to a first approximation may be neglected. This approximation will be made in the following analysis. $I(H;Q)$ is the mutual information between H and Q [22]. Using $I(H;Q) = S(H) - S(H/Q)$ and (3) we get (4) below.

$$S(P_e) \approx -P_e \cdot \log_2(N-1) + S(H) - I(H;Q) \quad (4)$$

To impose equality we let $\delta = I(Q;V)$ for $N=2$; where V is the binary discrete random variable representing the probability that the decision rule makes a correct decision. $V=1$ when $H=Q$. Otherwise $V=0$ [19]. Equation (4) can then be written more completely for $N=2$ as in (5) below.

$$S(P_e) \approx 1 - I(H;Q) \quad (5)$$

Equation (5) can be written in terms of the inverse function F as shown in (6).

$$P_e \approx F(S(H) - I(H;Q)) \quad (6)$$

F is a deterministic strictly monotonically increasing function that maps information theoretic quantities into a P_e . The quantity in (7) is the end to end information loss (IL) for the system.

$$IL \approx S(H) - I(H;Q) \quad (7)$$

Minimizing the information loss minimizes the system P_e .

The entropic quantity $S(H)$ is determined by the a priori probabilities of the outcomes of the random variable H , which correspond to the different target classes. Since F is a known function, the relation $P_e \approx F(S(H) - I(H;Q))$, for fixed $S(H)$, determines the mutual information $I(H;Q)$ needed to achieve a specified P_e . For example, for an equiprobable binary hypothesis scenario¹, $S(H) = 1$ Bit, $P_e \approx F(1 - I(H;Q))$. Specifying a desired P_e determines the amount of allowed IL.

¹ The selection of the uniform prior on H is for illustration purposes.

How the IL budget is spent as information cascades from the input collected signature space to the classifier output can be traded off. Fig. 2 is an abstract diagram indicating possible tradeoffs.

Figure 2. An abstract sketch of information flow tradeoffs.

Information losses within the channel may be studied with respect to various component design choices such as those in Table I. The Data Processing Inequality states that information can only be lost in the information channel as shown in (8).

$$I(H;X) \geq I(H;D) \geq I(H;Q) \quad (8)$$

Using the relationships in (4) and (8) the loss associated with each source within the channel can be characterized at certain points in the channel as shown in (9).

$$S(H) - I(H;X) \leq S(H) - I(H;D) \leq S(H) - I(H;Q) \quad (9)$$

Through the use of information theory based principles, a formal mathematical definition of component information loss is possible. The fundamental relationship between the entropy associated with the probability of error and the MI between the random variables H and Q becomes the basis for our study of system component information loss. From (4) we can see that all sources of increased entropy introduced in the channel will result in an increase in P_e . An increase in $S(P_e)$ will result in a reduction in $I(H;Q)$ and thus induce a loss in information flow and a degradation to the P_e .

IV. RESULTS

The results of the experiments outlined in Table 1 are presented below.

Fig. 3. Case 1: Component Information Loss and System Probability of Error as a Function of Signal-to-Noise Ratio, BW=500 MHz

In Fig. 3 the loss in information going from the encoded source \vec{X}_E to the discriminant D is quantified by $I(H;D)$. The information loss ranges from 0.88 Bits at 0 dB SNR to about 0.55 Bits at 20 dB SNR. Most of the information gain appears to be prior to 10 db SNR. Using equation (5) the Fano estimate of the system performance measure of P_e is observed to be equal to the actual P_e . Consistent with the trends in information loss, most of the reduction in P_e occurs prior to 12 dB SNR. In Fig. 3 the difference between measures $I(H;D)$ and $I(H;Q)$ show a loss of about 0.05 to 0.1 Bits of information in applying the discriminant to the algorithm decision rule. The significant overlap in \vec{X} space is realized as the loss in information associated with $I(H;D)$ which asymptotes to about 0.45 Bits.

In Fig. 4 the effects of bandwidth on the loss of information is illustrated. The trends are similar to those in Case 1 with $I(H;D)$ achieving most of the loss reduction and system performance (P_e) at about 500 MHz (approximately 0.55 Bits of loss). The loss in information at the discriminant point D ranges from .87 Bits at 100 MHz of BW and reduces to about 0.5 Bits at 1 GHz of BW. A loss of less than 0.1 Bits of information is incurred in applying the algorithm decision rule to the discriminant (D).

In Case 3 the effects of increased dimensionality in the feature space \vec{Y} are studied for the baseline conditions. Fig. 5 illustrates the reduction in information loss as a function of an increase in the number of modes within the feature \vec{Y} . By the time \vec{Y} is constructed using five modes the measure P_e reaches near full performance. In Fig. 6 the case 4 experiment results illustrate the loss of information due to limitations within the training signature process. Within the range of the similarity index, there clearly exists a knee in the curve between index 3 and index 5. Additional work is underway to compute $I(\vec{X}';\vec{X})$ for high dimensional signature spaces which will provide a more meaningful similarity index.

Fig. 4. Case 2: Component Information Loss and System Probability of Error as a Function of System Bandwidth, SNR=20 dB

Fig. 5. Case 3: Component Information Loss and System Probability of Error as a Function of Number of Modes in Feature Y, SNR=20 dB, BW=500 MHz

Fig. 6. Case 4: Component Information Loss and System Probability of Error as a Function of Training Process Similarity to Measured Signature Process, SNR=20 dB, BW=500 MHz

The results for all four cases are summarized in Table II below. The loss associated with various components is tabulated as a function of the four experiments (Cases 1-4). *{Note: the results for losses associated with the measurement of the signature process \tilde{X} are under evaluation at the time of the submission of this paper. Methods for computing discrete entropy for high dimensional data sets are being applied to computing the entropy of signature sets such as \tilde{X} . Completed results will be available at the final submission deadline.}*

TABLE III
INFORMATION LOSS BUDGET

System Component	Information Loss, Bits			
	Case 1 SNR	Case 2 BW	Case 3 Y	Case 4 (\tilde{X} , \tilde{X})
Source-to-Measurement (X)	TBP (TBP)*	TBP (TBP)*	TBP (TBP)*	TBP (TBP)*
Measurement-to-Discriminant (D)	0.55-0.88 (0.55)*	.45-.95 (.55)*	.03-.01 (.5)*	0.55-0.8
Decision Rule Application (Q)	< 0.05 (0.1)*	< 0.1 (0.1)*	< 0.05 (0.1)*	< 0.1 (0.1)

*Baseline conditions, ** TBP: To be provided in final draft

V. CONCLUSION

In general it appears that for this binary decision algorithm, several key observations can be made. With 1 Bit total information in the channel, the loss due to the application of the algorithm decision rule is small compared to that incurred in the transformation of the encoded signature to the discriminant D. *Additional insight will be available when the values of $I(H; \tilde{X})$ provide the loss associated with the measurement of the target class hypotheses. The computation of $I(H; \tilde{X})$ to be provided in the final submission will afford insight into the relative loss in the channel due to sensor design parameters such as the BW of the transmitted waveform.*

The selection of 500 MHz for transmit BW and five modes within \tilde{Y} appear to be good design choices given the information loss curves in Figures 2-4. A SNR of at least 10 dB is required to realize optimal performance. It also appears that the sensitivity to the selection of the number of modes within the feature design \tilde{Y} can be high when the number of modes is below a minimum cut-off.

Future efforts will include additional analysis and theory development involving the design of the radar exploitation system within the context of component level information loss.

REFERENCES

- [1] T. Ritchey, "Analysis and Synthesis", Systems Research (Journal of) Vol. 8, ISSN # 0731, No. 4, pp. 21-41, Revised Version 1996
- [2] P.M. Woodward, I.L Davies, "A Theory of Radar Information", *Philosophical Magazine*, Vol. 41, pp. 1001-1017, Oct. 1951.
- [3] P.M. Woodward, *Probability & Information Theory with Applications to Radar*, 2nd edition, Pergamon Press, 1964
- [4] C. E. Shannon, "A mathematical theory of communication," *Bell System Technical Journal*, Vol. 27, pp. 379-423 and 623-656, July and Oct., 1948
- [5] M. Bell, "Information Theory and Radar: Mutual Information and the Design and Analysis of Radar Waveforms and Systems", Ph.D. Dissertation, Department of Electrical Engineering, California Institute of Technology, 1988
- [6] A. Leshem, O. Naporstek, A. Nehorai, "Information Theoretic Adaptive Radar Waveform Design for Multiple Extended Targets", *IEEE Transactions on Selected Topics in Signal Processing*, Vol. 1, No. 1, June 2007
- [7] S. Sowelam, A. Tewfik, "Waveform Selection in Radar Target Classification", *IEEE Transactions on Information Theory*, Vol. 46, no. 3, May 2000
- [8] S. Kullback, R.A. Leibler, "On Information & Sufficiency", *Ann. Math. Stat.*, 22: pp. 79-86, 1951
- [9] S. Briles, "The Theory for, and the Demonstration of, Information Theory Applied to Radar Target Identification", Ph.D. Dissertation Kansas State University, 1992
- [10] A. M Home, D. Malvern "An information theory for the prediction of SAR target classification" in *Proc. for Algorithms for synthetic aperture radar imagery. Conference N°8, Orlando FL, 2001*, Vol. 4382, pp. 404-415
- [11] J.C. Principe, D. Xu, Q. Zhao, J.W. Fisher "Learning from Examples with Information Theoretic Criteria", *Journal of VLSI Signal Processing* 26, 61-77, 2000
- [12] J. O'Sullivan, M. DeVove, V. Kedia, M. Miller, "SAR ATR Performance Using a Conditionally Gaussian Model" *IEEE Transactions on Aerospace Electronics Systems* Vol.37, No. 1, Jan. 2001.
- [13] J. Malas, K. Pasala, "Information Theory Based Signature Analysis", *In the Proc. of 2007 IEEE Aerospace Conference*, Mar. 2007
- [14] E. Fishler, A. Haimovich, R. Blum, L. J. Cimini, D. Chizhik, and R. A. Valenuela, "Spatial diversity in radars-models and detection performance," *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing*, Vol. 3, no. 54, pp. 823-838, Mar. 2006
- [15] K. Forsythe and D. Bliss, "Waveform correlation and optimization issues for MIMO radar," in *Proc. 39th Asilomar Conf. Signals, Systems, and Computers*, Monterey, CA, 2005, pp. 1306-1310.
- [16] D. R. Fuhrmann and G. San Antonio, "Transmit beamforming for MIMO radar systems using partial signal correlation," *IEEE Transactions Aerospace Electronics Systems* Vol. 43, no. 4, Oct. 2007.
- [17] D. Bliss and K. Forsythe, "Multiple-input Multiple-output (MIMO) radar imaging: Degrees of freedom and resolution" in *Proc. 39th Asilomar Conf. Signals, Systems, and Computers*, Monterey, CA, 2003, pp. 54-59.
- [18] N. Tishby, F. Pereira, and W. Bialek. "The information bottleneck method" in *Proc. 37th Allerton Conf. on Communication and Computation*, 1999.
- [19] J. A. Cortese, "Information Theory and Radar Signal Processing", Air Force Research Lab, Georgia Institute of Technology College of Computing, Tech. Rep. Mar., 2009, Unpublished
- [20] N. Levanon, *Radar Principles*, John Wiley & Sons, 1988
- [21] K. Fukunaga, *Statistical Pattern Recognition*, Academic Press, 1990
- [22] T. Cover, J. Thomas, *Elements of Information Theory*, New York: Wiley, 1991
- [23] Approved for Public Release 13-JAN-10, case 88 ABW-10-0089